

MULTISCALE STUDY ON LOAD TRANSFER OF EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the load transfer ability of epoxy nanocomposites is investigated using a multiscale approach combined with molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and a homogenization-based finite element model. During the nanocomposites are deformed in uniaxial direction, the stress-strain responses for each phase, the particle and the matrix, are examined and the detailed structural changes are thoroughly observed in the atomistic scale. To reflect the load transfer characteristics with crosslinking in MD simulations, we proposed a homogenization-based continuum model considering interfacial imperfection.

1 INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resins are widely used as matrix phase materials in fiber-reinforced composites providing various industrial applications due to their high specific stiffness, high strength and ease in processing. With recent development of fabrication technique in the nanoscale, dramatic improvement in thermo-mechanical properties of epoxy with the incorporation of nano-sized reinforcing fillers has been observed and drawn huge attentions in various engineering fields. These favorable phenomena stem from the extremely large surface area to filler volume in the nanoscale. The interphase region around the filler surface entails different properties compared to those of bulk matrix due to filler-matrix interactions. Especially in well-dispersed nanocomposite systems, the interphase properties dominate over the characteristics of composites, resulting in a higher enhancing effect on nanocomposites [1].

Epoxy resins are engineering thermoset resins having distinct structures termed as crosslinks. During a curing process, strong covalent bonds are formed between resins and curing agents. Due to the network-like structures after crosslinking, the fundamental natures of epoxy polymer systems are strongly influenced by the curing conversion; polymer chain dynamics, thermodynamics characteristics, and mechanical properties are varied by the crosslink density of epoxy. Changes in fundamental characteristics of epoxy resins with the formation of crosslinks alter the degree of reinforcing in nanocomposite systems. Putz et al. [2] reported that the interphase effects in nanocomposites are substantially modified by crosslink densities of epoxy with experimental technique using dynamic scanning calorimetry (DSC). Recently, Kim et al. [3, 4] revealed the variation of interphase characteristics in terms of thermo-mechanical properties using MD simulations; decrease in interfacial interactions and interphase properties.

Considering the load transfer from the matrix to the reinforcing filler, it is generally agreed that strong interphase regions can lead better load transfer characteristics [5]. The fundamental mechanism behind the formation of interphase region around the embedded filler is the interfacial communication between the filler and matrix phase. In the previous work, it has been reported that the interfacial interactions are substantially influenced by the degree of crosslinking in thermoset-based nanocomposites, thus the interphase behavior is varied with crosslinking.

In this work, the load transfer characteristics of epoxy nanocomposites are investigated with the aid of MD simulations. Considering a wide range of crosslinking conversions, stress transfers from the epoxy matrix to the reinforcing filler are examined with monitoring the stress-strain behavior of each phase (matrix and filler) under the mechanical loading condition. To reflect the load transfer

characteristics of epoxy nanocomposites with the curing conversion, the continuum model based on finite element method with the homogenization scheme is proposed.

2 MODELING AND SIMULATION METHODOLOGY

In this section, detailed modeling procedures for establishing the epoxy nanocomposites model using MD simulations are described. Proper ensembles to equilibrate the molecular models and production runs are illustrated

2.1 Modeling of crosslinked epoxy nanocomposites

The chemical compositions of EPON862 and TETA are illustrated in **Fig. 1**. During the curing reaction, the carbon atoms in the epoxide group of EPON862 and the nitrogen atoms in the amine group of TETA are activated. Those activated atoms can be linked each other forming new covalent bonds, then crosslinked networks in epoxy polymers are produced.

Uncured bulk epoxy unit cell consisting of EPON862 and TETA was constructed using the Amorphous Cell module [5]. As a reinforcing filler, the spherical shape of silicon carbide (SiC) nanoparticle was imbedded into the epoxy matrix region. The target density of epoxy nanocomposites system was set to be 1.2 g/cm³ and the periodic boundary conditions were applied in x, y, and z directions. The initial molecular model for composites was minimized using the conjugate gradient method and equilibrated using NVT ensemble at 500 K. To mimic the curing reaction in epoxy system, the dynamic crosslinking scheme, a series of close contact detection and geometry optimization process, was implemented. The initial cutoff radius of 3.5 Å was considered to produce crosslinks between the possible reactive pairs (C and N). Once reactive pairs were decided, new covalent bond was formed and overall geometric topology was optimized and relaxed using NVT ensemble. Afterwards, a new round of close contact detection and optimization process was followed until the predefined conversion ratio was accomplished. If no more close contacts between potential reactive pairs were observed, the cutoff distance was increased and the crosslinking procedure was repeated iteratively. The overall schematic of crosslinking method is illustrated in **Fig. 2**. From 15% to 73%, various curing conversion rates were considered for epoxy/SiC nanocomposites system. After the crosslinking process, crosslinked epoxy nanocomposite unit cells were cooled down to 300 K using NVT ensemble and again equilibrated through NPT ensemble at 300 K and 1 atm.

2.2 Tensile simulation

Once the crosslinked epoxy nanocomposites with a wide range of crosslink conversions were established, uniaxial tensile mechanical loadings were imposed to the unit cells to investigate the load transfer characteristics of nanocomposites system. The tensile simulation was conducted using LAMMPS (Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator). To conduct uniaxial tensile simulation of crosslinked epoxies nanocomposites system, a small amount of displacement was applied to the unit cells with the predefined true strain rate of 10⁻⁶/ps using NPT ensemble. This sudden stretch leads the increase of the potential energy, resulting in increasing the internal stress of systems. After the cells were stretched, the systems were relaxed and this process was repeated again until the total strain of unit cells reached 20%. To reflect the Poisson's effect, the pressure perpendicular to the loading direction was set to 1 atm while cells were stretched. The time-averaged stress tensors corresponding to the tensile strains calculated from the virial theorem [11] for each step. The virial stresses are defined as the following equation,

$$\sigma_{ij} = \frac{1}{V} \left(\sum_i^N m_i v_i v_j + \frac{1}{2} \sum_i^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N (r_i - r_j) F_{ij} \right) \quad (1)$$

where V is the atomic volume, N is the number of atom, v_i is the thermal excitation velocity of atom i , m_i and r_i are the mass and position of atom i , and F_{ij} is the atomic force on atom i due to atom j , respectively. The stiffness components for normal and transversal directions of the model can be simply obtained from the virial stress for all constituent atoms by using Hooke's law.

During the tensile simulation, the stress-strain behavior for each phase, SiC particle and epoxy matrix, was thoroughly monitored to reveal the stress transfer characteristics from the matrix to the reinforcing filler region with varying curing conversion of epoxy matrix.

Figure 1. Chemical structures of (a) epoxy resin TGAP, and (b) curing agent DDS.

Figure 2. Schematic of crosslinking methodology.

3 MOLECULAR DYNAMICS RESULTS

Detailed stress-strain behavior for the particle and epoxy matrix phase was observed during the tensile loading simulations. Before discussing about the load transfer ability of nanocomposites, mechanical properties and overall stress-strain behavior are examined. As can be seen in **Fig. 3(a)**, Young's modulus and density increase with the increasing crosslink density, since the epoxy system becomes stiffer and densely packed with the formation of more crosslinks. In terms of the overall stress-strain behavior of epoxy nanocomposites, highly crosslinked system shows higher stress response as shown in **Fig. 3(b)**.

To investigate the load transfer ability of nanocomposites, the stress-strain responses for the imbedded reinforcing filler and matrix phase are compared in **Fig. 4**. As given in **Fig. 4(a)**, the stress-strain response of the matrix phase shows a similar trend with the response of nanocomposites (**Fig. 3(b)**); almost identical stress value with the nanocomposites. In **Fig. 4(b)**, it is obvious that the degree of stress transfer to the filler phase is significantly attributed to the crosslink density of epoxy matrix. In highly crosslinked nanocomposites (73% of curing conversion), the reinforcing particles tend to accommodate more stresses when the mechanical loading is exerted on the nanocomposites. The result

clearly indicates that epoxy nanocomposites with a higher crosslink density exhibit better load transfer ability.

Figure 3. Mechanical properties and stress-strain response of epoxy/SiC nanocomposites with varying curing conversion; (a) Young's modulus and density, and (b) stress-strain curve.

Figure 4. Stress-strain response of (a) matrix and (b) reinforcing particle with varying crosslink density.

4 MULTISCALE MODEL

Based on the observation in the atomistic level with the MD simulations, we propose the continuum-scale finite element (FE) model that reflects the load transfer characteristics in nanocomposites. The FE model [6, 7] consists of the particle and matrix phase which are equivalent to the molecular model constructed in the previous MD simulations. Similar to the tensile simulation in MD, the uniaxial loading is applied to the FE model while keeping the stress tensor perpendicular to the loading direction at zero.

The elasto-plastic behaviors of the nanocomposites from the MD simulations were used in the FE simulations. Herein, to bridge the MD results with the continuum model, the secant moduli method-based approach is employed with the assumption that the individual phase are uniform without causing the spatial local fluctuation. For the perfect interfacial bonding between the two phases, the microscopic force equilibrium equation is given as:

$$\int_{\Omega_{comp}} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C}^{sec} \mathbf{B} \chi dV_y = \int_{\Omega_{comp}} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C}^{sec} dV_y \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{C}^{sec} is the secant moduli tensor of each continuous phase, and χ is the microscopic displacement fields subjected to the unit macroscopic strain fields. Then, the effective stress tensor of the phase and the macroscopic homogenized stress tensor can be obtained as given in Eq. (3).

$$\Sigma_r = \left\{ \frac{1}{|Y|} \times \int_{\Omega_r} \mathbf{C}^{\text{sec}} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}\chi) dV_y \right\} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{comp}}, r \in \{em, p, comp\} \quad (3)$$

where Ω_{comp} is the domain of the unit cell, 'em', 'p', and 'comp' are denoted as the effective matrix, the nanoparticle, and the nanocomposites, respectively. In this study, we obtained the secant moduli tensor which makes the difference between the MD results and the FE model. To take into account the interfacial imperfection with the crosslink conversion of epoxy in the nanocomposites, the interfacial springs in the normal direction at the interface are implemented. The results from the present FE model are illustrated in **Fig. 5**. As can be seen in **Fig. 5(a)**, the present continuum model provides a reasonable prediction in terms of the load transfer to the reinforcing filler in the nanocomposites with varying curing conversions. In **Fig. 5(b)**, the interfacial spring constants with crosslinking are given.

Figure 5. Load transfer characteristics with FE model considering the interfacial imperfection: (a) the stress-strain curve of particle phase from MD simulations and the continuum model, and (b) interfacial spring constant with crosslinking

5 CONCLUSION

In the present work, detailed load transfer characteristics of epoxy/SiC nanocomposites are investigated using MD simulations. The MD results reveal that the load transfer ability from the matrix to the reinforcing filler in nanocomposites is improved as the crosslink conversion of epoxy matrix increases. To reflect the observation in the molecular level into the continuum scale, a homogenization-based FE model is proposed. Considering the interfacial imperfection with the level of crosslinking, the present continuum model provide a reasonable prediction in terms of the load transfer characteristics of epoxy nanocomposites as compared to the MD results.

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